

MODELING COMMITMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS

Allan Deanmacgy S. Cruz

*Centro Escolar University, Philippines
Senior High School Department, National University, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

In the present where technology is deeply embedded in educational practices, understanding what drives teacher satisfaction and commitment becomes increasingly important, particularly among younger educators who bring new expectations and work values to the profession. While leadership, work-life balance, and school culture have been well-documented as critical influences, the roles of technology integration and teaching experience remain underexplored, especially in private school settings. This study explores the various factors influencing job satisfaction and commitment among 129 private school teachers from Caloocan and Quezon City. The findings highlight the significant role of leadership support, organizational culture, work-life balance, and manageable workload in shaping job satisfaction, which in turn strongly predicts teacher commitment. Notably, work-life balance emerged as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction, while job satisfaction had the greatest effect on commitment. In contrast, years of teaching experience and technology integration were not found to be significant predictors. These results suggest that teachers' emotional well-being, professional relationships, and supportive work conditions matter more than tenure or access to tools in fostering engagement and long-term dedication. The study contributes to a deeper understanding of what drives teacher satisfaction and commitment in the Philippine private school context and offers practical implications for developing retention-focused school leadership and policy strategies.

Keywords: *Job Satisfaction, Teacher Commitment, Organizational Culture, Work-life Balance, Technology Integration*

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction and commitment are essential components of a teacher's overall well-being and professional success. Job satisfaction refers to the positive feelings teachers have about their work, often influenced by factors like work environment, resources, and relationships with colleagues. While job commitment is the dedication and attachment a teacher feels toward their profession, which often translates into longer tenure and higher levels of engagement. These two factors are closely linked, as satisfied teachers are more likely to remain committed to their roles, leading to better educational outcomes for students. In the context of teaching, both satisfaction and commitment play a critical role in reducing turnover rates, improving productivity, and maintaining a positive school environment.

Despite existing research on teacher satisfaction and commitment, there remains a need to focus more intently on young educators, a cohort characterized by high job mobility and shifting professional values (Bordey, 2024). As relatively new teachers increasingly enter the workforce, their presence introduces new dynamics in schools, especially in the present, where digital technology is no longer novel but deeply embedded in teaching practices. In this context, the emphasis has shifted from simply adopting technology to critically evaluating how it is used, raising questions around its alignment with pedagogy, ethical implications, and its impact on engagement and retention.

In the Philippine setting, marked by systemic challenges such as poverty, inequality, and a chronic teacher shortage (Lee-Brago, 2024), understanding the evolving needs of a younger, tech-savvy workforce is vital. While work-life balance, organizational culture, and leadership support have been consistently linked to satisfaction and commitment, the integration of technology into teaching and the length of professional experience may now play a more decisive role.

Access to and alignment of technology with the curriculum—such as its ability to make lessons more engaging and meaningful—may contribute differently to the job satisfaction of novice teachers compared to their more experienced counterparts. These variations in experience and technological integration warrant closer examination, especially as job satisfaction is closely linked to performance outcomes (Deslate & Pallada, 2023) and supportive environments have been shown to reduce burnout and attrition (Bona, 2020). In this light, understanding how these factors interact in the present digital educational landscape becomes essential for developing more responsive and sustainable teacher retention strategies.

This study aims to develop and validate a model using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to examine how various factors influence job satisfaction and commitment among private school teachers in Caloocan and Quezon City. The study specifically investigates the relationships between job satisfaction, commitment, and factors such as leadership support, organizational culture, work-life balance, workload and job demands. It also focuses on technology integration, and years of teaching experience as predictors of job satisfaction and commitment. By developing a model, the study seeks to identify which of these factors have the most significant impact on teachers' job satisfaction and commitment, and how they interrelate to predict

these outcomes. By exploring these variables, the study will provide a clearer understanding of contextual factors that shape teachers' job satisfaction and commitment, which can inform educational policy, leadership practices, and professional development programs.

Theoretical Model Related to Commitment and Job Satisfaction

One widely accepted framework for understanding employee motivation, satisfaction, and commitment is the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory. Originally developed by Demerouti et al. (2001) and further refined by Bakker and Demerouti (2007), the JD-R model suggests that workplace conditions can be categorized into two broad dimensions: job demands and job resources. Job demands refer to physical, psychological, or organizational aspects of a job that require sustained effort and are associated with physiological or psychological costs—such as workload, time pressure, or emotionally demanding interactions. On the other hand, job resources are elements that help employees achieve work goals, reduce job demands, and promote personal growth, learning, and development.

In the context of this study, the JD-R theory offers a useful lens to understand the dynamics behind teachers' job satisfaction and commitment in private basic education schools. When teachers face demanding workloads without the support of sufficient resources, they may experience burnout, disengagement, and ultimately lower satisfaction. Existing studies emphasize the importance of leadership support, organizational culture, and work-life balance as critical job resources that enhance satisfaction and foster commitment. However, limited research has explored how newer variable, such as technology integration and years of teaching experience, contribute to these outcomes. Addressing this gap, the present study seeks to develop a structural model that identifies which factors most significantly influence teacher satisfaction and commitment, offering timely insights for educational leadership and policy in today's evolving school environments.

Workload and Job Demands influence Work-life Balance

Work-life balance for teachers involves time for personal activities, flexibility for personal needs, and a supportive work environment. A manageable workload that aligns with professional responsibilities is essential for achieving this balance, allowing for lesson preparation without feeling overwhelmed.

Workload and job demands are key predictors of work-life balance. Effective workload management improves satisfaction and balance (Bar-Tal et al., 2020), while work pressure affects psychological needs (Tack, 2019). Reducing classroom stress supports well-being (Power, 2023), whereas unmanaged demands can cause anger and anxiety (Membiela, 2023). Perceived overload and time pressure also impair well-being (Helm et al., 2024). In addition, teacher well-being, closely linked to work-life balance, suffers under high job demands (Silva et al., 2023; Hascher & Waber, 2021). Excessive workload contributes to burnout, stress, and turnover intentions (Yin et al., 2019; Gundlach et al., 2024), underscoring the importance of workload management in maintaining work-life balance.

Altogether, work-life balance is profoundly shaped by workload and job demands, as these factors directly affect teachers' well-being, professional satisfaction, and overall quality of life. A manageable workload and clear job expectations are crucial for fostering an environment where teachers can achieve their personal and professional goals without undue stress. When workload and job demands are effectively addressed, teachers experience reduced stress, enhanced well-being, and improved job satisfaction, creating a harmonious balance between their professional responsibilities and personal lives. This balance is essential for sustaining motivation, preventing burnout, and ensuring long-term success in the teaching profession.

Leadership Support influence Organizational Culture

Leadership support plays a vital role in shaping school organizational culture, influencing teachers' experiences, development, and work environment. Effective communication, mentorship, and involvement in decision-making foster trust, collaboration, and alignment between personal and institutional goals. This leadership-driven culture enhances respect, community, and continuous improvement.

Leadership support directly predicts teacher satisfaction, especially among second-career educators (Bar-Tal et al., 2020), and promotes self-efficacy through structured placements and growth opportunities (Power, 2023). Professional development is also strengthened in environments where leaders create learning opportunities (Tack, 2019) and influence how teachers perceive the value and relevance of their work (Membiela, 2023). Moreover, leadership aligns with key job resources such as autonomy and peer support, reinforcing a positive culture (Silva et al., 2023). Leadership-driven resources like social support and task clarity also boost satisfaction and well-being (Helm et al., 2024).

As a whole, leadership support significantly influences organizational culture by fostering professional growth, enhancing teacher autonomy, and promoting well-being. These elements collectively contribute to a thriving school environment where teachers feel valued, supported, and committed to their professional roles.

Work-life Balance, Organizational Culture, Years of Experience, and Technology Integration influence Job Satisfaction

Teacher job satisfaction is shaped by interrelated factors such as work-life balance, organizational culture, years of experience, and technology integration. Managing personal and professional roles significantly impacts satisfaction; job demands reduce well-being, while autonomy and peer support enhance it (Silva et al., 2023). Meaningful work and altruistic motives also help teachers balance life and work, increasing fulfillment (Tonna & Calleja, 2021). Similarly, a positive organizational culture fosters collaboration, motivation, and well-being (Silva et al., 2023), while resources like social support and task clarity help mitigate overload (Helm et al., 2024). Meeting psychological needs through autonomy and relatedness contributes to satisfaction (Tack, 2019), as do social trust and institutional support (Hascher & Waber, 2021; Li & Yao, 2022). Also, experience influences satisfaction—veteran teachers often enjoy greater confidence and resilience

(Power, 2023), while newer ones benefit from mentorship (Bar-Tal et al., 2020). However, experience also affects attitudes toward technology; newer teachers tend to embrace it more readily (Xu & Jiang, 2022). In the same way, technology integration is a key contributor to satisfaction, especially when teachers are competent and confident in its use (Nurgaliyeva et al., 2023; Xu & Jiang, 2022). When effectively applied, technology reduces workload and enhances instructional quality, promoting overall fulfillment.

The interplay of work-life balance, organizational culture, years of experience, and technology integration provides a comprehensive understanding of job satisfaction among teachers. Research consistently highlights how these factors influence job satisfaction, emphasizing the need to foster supportive environments, provide opportunities for professional growth, and empower educators with technological tools that enhance their teaching experiences and overall fulfillment.

Job Satisfaction and Years of Experience influence Commitment

Teacher commitment is shaped by multiple factors, particularly job satisfaction and years of experience. Job satisfaction is a key predictor of commitment, as it enhances teachers' ability to manage stress and remain engaged in their roles (Bar-Tal et al., 2020). It also fosters self-efficacy, boosting confidence and professional dedication (Power, 2023). Similarly, years of experience similarly strengthen commitment by increasing autonomy and self-efficacy, which reduce attrition (De Neve & Devos, 2016). Experienced teachers often draw motivation from intrinsic values, developing resilience and purpose over time (Tonna & Calleja, 2021; Gratacós & Ciesielkiewicz, 2021). Support from peers and leadership further enhances their sense of belonging and institutional attachment (Babic et al., 2023). The synergy between job satisfaction and experience deepens commitment, especially when job resources like autonomy and support are present (Silva et al., 2023). Clarity, relevance, and social backing also drive satisfaction and sustained engagement (Helm et al., 2024).

In conclusion, the literature consistently supports the idea that both job satisfaction and years of experience play crucial roles in fostering teacher commitment. Satisfied teachers are more likely to remain in the profession, while experienced teachers develop stronger bonds with their institutions over time. Together, these factors create an environment that promotes long-term engagement, retention, and dedication to the teaching profession, ultimately contributing to the success and stability of educational institutions.

Proposed Structural Equation Model

Based on the readings, the researcher proposed a PLS-SEM involving exogenous variables which are leadership support (LS), technology integration (TI), workload and job demands (WJ), and years of experience (YE), and endogenous variables which are organizational culture (OC), job satisfaction (JS), commitment (C), and work-life balance (WB). It has two sub-models (see Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model for the Variables

In figure 1, this is the proposed hypothesized or measurement model (outer model) for the variables. This specifies the relation between the variables and their observed variables. Also, this was used to examine the validity and reliability of each construct contained in the questionnaire.

Figure 2: Structural Model for the Variables

On the other hand, Figure 2 is the structural model (inner model) for the latent variables. It shows the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables. Then, the significance and strength of the hypothesized relationships between these variables in this model will be tested.

Research Questions

Understanding the factors that shape teachers' job satisfaction and commitment is essential in fostering a supportive and sustainable educational environment. In private schools, where teachers often face unique organizational dynamics, workload expectations, and leadership structures, identifying the variables that influence their satisfaction and commitment becomes crucial. Considering these complexities, this study examines how leadership support, organizational culture, workload and job demands, technology integration, work-life balance, and years of experience interact to shape teachers' professional experiences. To guide the investigation, the following research questions were formulated:

1. How does workload and job demands influence work-life balance?
2. How does leadership support influence organizational culture?
3. How do work-life balance, organizational culture, years of experience and technology integration influence job satisfaction?
4. How do job satisfaction and years of experience influence commitment?

METHODOLOGY

This study examined whether a relationship among job satisfaction, commitment and various factors; and develop a model that explains and predicts the relationships. The factors considered include leadership support, organizational culture, work-life balance, workload and job demands, technology integration, and years of teaching experience.

Sample of the Study

The researcher utilized G*Power, a statistical software, to calculate the necessary sample size for the study with multiple predictors. Using a model with four predictors, an effect size of 0.15, a power level of 0.95, and a significance level of 0.05, the minimum required number of participants was determined to be 129. Therefore, the sample size for this study consists of 129 private school teachers. The demographic profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Subscale	Frequency	Percentages
Years of Experience	1-4	71	58.8
	More than 4	58	41.2

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents have 1-4 years of teaching experience. These findings indicate a relatively younger teaching workforce primarily focused on non-STEM fields.

Construction and Validation of the Instrument

The researcher reviewed related studies to identify key constructs influencing teachers' job satisfaction and commitment, including leadership support, organizational culture, work-life balance, technology integration, and workload. Indicators for each construct were developed, and the questionnaire was validated by three academic experts.

A pilot test with 30 respondents was conducted to assess reliability and validity. Indicators with outer loadings below 0.60 were removed (Ayanwale et al., 2022). The instrument's quality was further evaluated using composite reliability (≥ 0.70), average variance extracted (≥ 0.50), and Cronbach's alpha (≥ 0.70) (Cheung et al., 2024).

Initially composed of 24 indicators across seven constructs on a 4-point scale, the final validated questionnaire was refined to 23 indicators, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Rating Scale Items of the Study

Code	Item
C1	1. I am committed to my school's mission and values.
C2	2. I plan to continue at my current school for the foreseeable future.
C3	3. I feel a sense of belonging to my school community.
C4	4. I would put in extra effort to help my school succeed.
JS1	5. I feel valued as a teacher at my school.
JS2	6. I look forward to coming to work each day.
JS3	7. I would recommend my school as a good place to work.
LS1	8. There is open communication between teachers and school leaders regarding concerns and suggestions.
LS2	9. I received professional guidance and mentorship from school leaders.
LS3	10. I feel involved in decisions that affect my work environment and teaching.
OC1	11. There is a strong sense of community among the staff at my school.
OC2	12. Teachers are treated with respect and dignity at my school.
OC3	13. School promotes a culture of continuous improvement.
OC4	14. Collaboration among teachers is encouraged and supported.
TI1	15. I have access to modern educational technology for teaching.
TI2	16. The technology I use makes my teaching more engaging for students.
TI3	17. Technology is well-aligned with the curriculum I teach.
WB1	18. I have sufficient time for hobbies, relaxation, and activities unrelated to work.

WB2	19. I have flexibility in my work schedule to accommodate personal needs and emergencies.
WB3	20. My school administration provides adequate support to help me maintain a healthy balance between work and personal life.
WJ1	21. I feel that my workload is appropriate for my role and manageable within my working hours.
WJ2	22. I can allocate sufficient time to effectively prepare for and deliver lessons.
WJ3	23. My workload supports my ability to achieve my professional goals without making me feel overwhelmed.

Data Collection

The researcher used Microsoft Forms to create an online survey, which was distributed to teachers known to the researcher residing in Caloocan and Quezon City. Additionally, colleagues were asked to assist in recruiting other private school teachers encouraging them to voluntarily complete the survey. The survey remained open for nearly four weeks, from November 16 to December 16, 2024 before data collection was concluded.

Data Analysis

The study employed PLS-SEM using Smart PLS software, version 4.1.0.9, to analyze the data collected through the research instrument (Ringle et al., 2024). The software facilitated evaluations for both the measurement model and the structural model.

For the measurement model, the analysis included assessments of outer loadings (OLs), Cronbach's alpha (CA), composite reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), variance inflation factor for the outer model (VIF_{OM}), Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratios, and the Fornell-Larcker criterion.

For the structural model, the analysis covered VIF for the inner model (VIF_{IM}), standardized path coefficients (β), t-values, p-values, Cohen's effect size (f^2). The software also provided a summary of the results for all assessments.

RESULTS

Measurement Model Analysis

Table 3. Construct Validity and Reliability

Construct	Items	Loadings	CA	CR	AVE	VIF _{OM}
Commitment (C)	C1	0.793	0.834	0.837	0.668	1.748
	C2	0.791				1.656
	C3	0.856				2.085
	C4	0.828				1.932
Job Satisfaction (JS)	JS1	0.901	0.867	0.867	0.790	2.492

	JS2	0.872				2.053
	JS3	0.892				2.336
Leadership Support (LS)	LS1	0.895				2.226
	LS2	0.855	0.857	0.862	0.777	1.950
	LS3	0.895				2.347
Organizational Culture (OC)	OC1	0.861				2.260
	OC2	0.834	0.826	0.842	0.656	2.076
	OC3	0.731				1.751
	OC4	0.810				1.999
Technology Integration (TI)	TI1	0.785				1.541
	TI2	0.896	0.826	0.846	0.743	2.416
	TI3	0.901				2.300
Work-life Balance (WB)	WB1	0.895				2.669
	WB2	0.937	0.880	0.883	0.808	3.577
	WB3	0.862				2.160
Workload and Job Demands (WJ)	WJ1	0.862				2.043
	WJ2	0.865	0.855	0.863	0.775	2.026
	WJ3	0.913				2.476

Table 3 presents the construct validity and reliability of the measurement model. The analysis tested OLS of each indicator (≥ 0.60), CA (≥ 0.70), CR (≥ 0.70), and AVE (≥ 0.50) of each construct were tested. All 23 indicators were retained, with OLS ranging from 0.731 to 0.937. In addition, based on CA and CR estimates exceeded 0.70 for all constructs, ranging from 0.826 to 0.880 and 0.837 to 0.883 respectively. Similarly, all AVE values surpassed the threshold of 0.50. The VIF for outer model was also evaluated to check for potential multicollinearity among the indicators used to measure the latent constructs. The VIF values, range from 1.541 to 3.577 were below the recommended threshold of 5 (Hair et al., 2022), indicating no significant multicollinearity. Overall, the measurement model demonstrates adequate reliability, validity, and absence of significant multicollinearity, supported by satisfactory OLS, CA, CR, AVE estimates, and acceptable VIF values.

Table 4. Heterotrait-monotrait Ratios of the Construct in the Model

	C	JS	LS	OC	TI	WB	WJ
C							
JS	0.866						
LS	0.456	0.569					
OC	0.503	0.677	0.761				
TI	0.475	0.571	0.409	0.463			
WB	0.674	0.818	0.500	0.466	0.616		
WJ	0.586	0.693	0.361	0.398	0.515	0.828	

Table 4 shows the discriminant validity of the constructs, assessed using the HTMT ratio of correlations. Based on the criterion for discriminant validity, HTMT values should

be less than or equal to 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015). All constructs in the model had HTMT ratios below this threshold.

Table 5. Fornell-Larcker Criterion of the Construct in the Model

	C	JS	LS	OC	TI	WB	WJ
C	0.817						
JS	0.738	0.889					
LS	0.392	0.497	0.881				
OC	0.421	0.585	0.648	0.810			
TI	0.388	0.487	0.347	0.389	0.862		
WB	0.579	0.712	0.440	0.413	0.523	0.899	
WJ	0.496	0.599	0.311	0.346	0.432	0.723	0.880

Table 5 supports the HTMT ratios of the constructs in the outer model. According to Hair et al. (2022), the square root of the AVE (diagonal values) for each construct should be higher than the highest correlation with any other construct in the model. The square roots of the AVE for the reflective constructs C (0.818), JS (0.889), LS (0.881), OC (0.810), TI (0.862), WB (0.899) and WJ (0.880) are all greater than the correlations of these constructs with other latent variables, indicating that all constructs are valid measures of unique concepts.

Based on the results from Tables 4 and 5, it can be concluded that the constructs in the model demonstrate discriminant validity. Overall, both convergent and discriminant validity assessments confirm the validity of the constructs in the model.

Structural Model Analysis

Table 6. Variance Inflation Factor Values in the Structural Model

Path	VIF _{IM}
Job Satisfaction (JS) → Commitment (C)	1.002
Leadership Support (LS) → Organizational Culture (OC)	1.000
Organizational Culture (OC) → Job Satisfaction (JS)	1.277
Technology Integration (TI) → Job Satisfaction (JS)	1.477
Work-life Balance (WB) → Job Satisfaction (JS)	1.000
Workload and Job Demands (WJ) → Work-life Balance (WB)	1.517
Years of Experience (YE) → Commitment (C)	1.002
Years of Experience (YE) → Job Satisfaction (JS)	1.036

Table 6 presents the VIF values for the inner model to assess potential multicollinearity issues among all combinations of endogenous and corresponding exogenous latent variables. According to Hair et al. (2022), VIF values for all sets of predictor constructs in the inner model should be below 5, which is considered an acceptable threshold for PLS-SEM. Since all VIF values fall within the range of 1.000 to 1.517, this indicates that there are no multicollinearity issues in the inner model.

Table 7. R-square of the Endogenous Latent Variables

Construct	R-square	R-square adjusted
C	0.546	0.545
JS	0.616	0.614
OC	0.420	0.419
WB	0.523	0.523

Table 7 shows the R-square value of the constructs C, JS, OC, and WB. The R^2 value of 54.60% suggest that commitment is accounted for by its predictor which is job satisfaction. Also, the R^2 value of 61.60% suggests that organizational culture and work-life balance together explain 61.60% of the variance in job satisfaction. Additionally, organizational culture ($R^2=42.0\%$) and work-life balance ($R^2=52.3\%$) are explained by their respective predictors, leadership support and workload and job demands.

Table 8. Standardized Path Coefficient for Structural Model

Hypothesis	Path	β	T-value	P-value	f^2	Remarks
H_1	JS→C	0.737	17.656	0.000	1.193	Accepted
H_2	LS→OC	0.648	13.864	0.000	0.724	Accepted
H_3	OC→JS	0.338	5.767	0.000	0.233	Accepted
H_4	TI→JS	0.085	1.327	0.184	0.013	Not Accepted
H_5	WB→JS	0.723	14.155	0.000	1.097	Accepted
H_6	WJ→WB	0.526	8.503	0.000	0.474	Accepted
H_7	YE→C	0.160	0.466	0.641	0.002	Not Accepted
H_8	YE→JS	0.249	0.746	0.455	0.005	Not Accepted

Table 8 presents the standardized path coefficients of the structural model, which indicate the strength and direction of relationship between the latent variables. The direct relationship between the latent variables; H_1 JS→C ($\beta=0.737$, p-value=0.000, $f^2=1.193$), H_2 LS→OC ($\beta=0.648$, p-value=0.000, $f^2=0.724$), H_3 OC→JS ($\beta=0.338$, p-value=0.000, $f^2=0.233$), H_4 TI→JS ($\beta=0.085$, p-value=0.184, $f^2=0.013$), H_5 WB→JS ($\beta=0.723$, p-value=0.000, $f^2=1.097$), H_6 WJ→WB ($\beta=0.526$, p-value=0.000, $f^2=0.474$), H_7 YE→C ($\beta=0.160$, p-value=0.641, $f^2=0.002$), and H_8 YE→JS ($\beta=0.249$, p-value=0.455, $f^2=0.005$). Among these nine hypotheses tested, five were significant (H_1 , H_2 , H_3 , H_5 , and H_6) and four insignificant (H_4 , H_7 , and H_8).

Among these tested relationships, the strongest effect was observed for WB→JS, indicating that work-life balance plays a significant role in shaping job satisfaction, with large effect size. Similarly, JS→C was observed to have strong effect, indicating job satisfaction is a key determinant of commitment, with large effect size. On the other hand, the paths TI→JS, YE→C, and YE→JS were not significant, suggesting technology integration and years of experience have negligible and statistically non-significant effect on commitment and job satisfaction, which may indicate its limited relevance.

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to examine how factors such as leadership support (LS), organizational culture (OC), work-life balance (WB), workload and job demands (WJ), technology integration (TI), and years of teaching experience (YE) affect job satisfaction (JS) and commitment (C) among private school teachers in Caloocan and Quezon City. This research adds to the existing knowledge on job satisfaction and commitment within the Philippines' K-12 education system. Eight hypotheses were proposed to investigate the relationships between these factors, job satisfaction, and commitment. Five of the hypotheses, including those involving LS, OC, WB, WJ, JS, and C, were found to be significant. However, it was discovered that YE does not predict JS or C, and TI does not influence JS.

One of the findings of this study is that years of experience did not show a significant effect on job satisfaction and commitment, as indicated by the path coefficients: $YE \rightarrow C$ ($\beta=0.160$, $p\text{-value}=0.641$, $f^2=0.002$), and $YE \rightarrow JS$ ($\beta=0.249$, $p\text{-value}=0.455$, $f^2=0.005$). This implies that even teachers with only a few years of experience may already feel a deep sense of commitment and satisfaction if they perceive a strong alignment with school values, respectful relationship, and supportive leadership. This result appears to diverge from earlier studies that associate longer professional experience with increased job satisfaction and organizational commitment. For instance, Gratacós et al. (2021) argue that accumulated experience builds resilience and skills that foster long-term dedication. Similarly, Power (2023) found a positive relationship between experience and satisfaction, citing the benefits of established routines, increased confidence, and professional resilience among seasoned teachers. In addition, Silva et al. (2023) and Helm et al. (2024) highlighted how experienced teachers tend to benefit from greater autonomy, task clarity, and access to social support, which are factors that relates to higher levels of satisfaction and commitment.

Similarly, technology integration does not have a significant influence on job satisfaction, as indicated by the path coefficient ($\beta=0.085$, $p\text{-value}=0.184$, $f^2=0.013$). This means that teacher's job satisfaction is less about the availability of tools and more about the human experience within the workplace. Teachers value meaningful relationships, leadership support, and work-life balance more than whether or not they have technology access. This is especially important in places like the Philippines, where problems such as slow internet, lack of proper equipment, and limited training for teachers may prevent them from using technology effectively. Because of this, having access to technology doesn't always lead to greater job satisfaction. The difference in results suggests that technology helps more in schools with better resources, where internet, equipment, and support are already in place. But in schools with fewer resources, technology can feel like a burden instead of a help especially if teachers don't get enough training or support to use it properly.

Furthermore, the R^2 values reveal that the predictors explained 61.60% of the variance in job satisfaction. This finding demonstrates the substantial contribution of organizational culture and work-life balance in shaping teachers' job satisfaction. Meanwhile, job satisfaction explained 54.60% of the variance in commitment. The significance of these constructs is further supported by the studies of Silva et al. (2023),

who highlighted the positive impact of a supportive organizational culture on job satisfaction, and Power (2023), who emphasized that high satisfaction strengthens commitment. Additionally, Helm et al. (2024) underscore the importance of task clarity and social support, which buffer job stressors and contribute to higher satisfaction. These findings illustrate that when teachers experience a positive work environment and balance between professional and personal lives, they are more likely to feel satisfied with their roles and remain committed to their profession. In contrary, Nurgaliyeva et al. (2023) and Xu and Jiang (2022) found that technology integration significantly enhances job satisfaction by improving teaching competencies, reducing administrative burden, and allowing teachers to focus more on meaningful instruction.

Work-life balance is the strongest predictor of job satisfaction ($\beta=0.723$, p -value=0.000, $f^2=1.097$). Managing workload and job demands enhances this balance, leading to greater satisfaction (Bar-Tal et al., 2020; Power, 2023). Teachers with balanced personal and professional lives report more positive emotions and higher job satisfaction. In addition, job satisfaction has a significant influence on commitment ($\beta=0.737$, p -value=0.000, $f^2=1.193$). Satisfied teachers—especially those with access to autonomy and support—show stronger professional commitment (Bar-Tal et al., 2020; Silva et al., 2023).

Overall, the findings of this study emphasize that teacher satisfaction and commitment are shaped more by the quality of the work environment and relational support than by tenure or technology availability alone. The results highlight the central role of work-life balance, supportive leadership, and a positive school culture in fostering satisfaction and long-term commitment among teachers. While prior literature has pointed to the benefits of experience and digital tools, this study shows that these factors may not hold the same weight in resource-constrained or evolving educational contexts, such as those found in parts of the Philippines.

Conclusions

This study highlights the critical role of leadership support, organizational culture, work-life balance, workload and job demands, technology integration, and years of experience influence job satisfaction and commitment among private school teachers in Caloocan and Quezon City. The findings revealed that work-life balance emerged as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction, while job satisfaction itself had the most substantial effect on teacher's commitment. In contrast, years of teaching experience and technology integration did not significantly influence job satisfaction or commitment. These results emphasize that teacher's emotional experiences, professional relationships, and well-being matter more than tenure or tool availability in shaping their engagement with the profession. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of what drives teacher satisfaction and commitment in the Philippine K-12 context, particularly in private schools facing challenges related to resources, workload, and retention.

Recommendations

Educational administrators and policymakers should design and implement policies that foster a supportive work environment, offering flexibility and balance, and nurturing a strong organizational culture to retain teachers and keep them motivated. Future research may focus on building these findings by exploring generational differences in teacher expectations, testing interventions to strengthen leadership and work-life balance, and examining how digital tools can be better implemented in low-resource settings to support teachers, not strain. In addition, future research should include a larger sample across different cities in National Capital Region, to further validate the findings. And lastly, exploring the differences and similarities in teachers' perspectives across various grade levels and specializations could provide a more comprehensive understanding of their views on job satisfaction and commitment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that all ethical standards were rigorously upheld throughout the conduct of this study. Informed consent was secured from all participants after clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights, including the option to withdraw at any time without penalty. Respondent anonymity was protected by separating identifying information from survey data, and all information gathered was treated with strict confidentiality. The welfare of participants was prioritized at all stages of the research. The researcher declares no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was meticulously avoided through proper citation and acknowledgment of all sources. Furthermore, the analysis and interpretation of findings were carried out objectively and without bias, with all results utilized solely for academic and research purposes.

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